

Military metaphors in the discourses of the pandemic in two post-Yugoslav states

Literal associations and historization of crisis

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The present study contributes to the growing body of work on the pandemic-time use of the WAR metaphor in public discourse, by focusing specifically on military metaphors in the media discourses of two post-Yugoslav, post-conflict states. Using the approach of Critical Metaphor Analysis, the paper explores the discursive realizations of the WAR metaphor in this context, with a particular focus on metaphor extension, metaphor entailments, and effects of earlier conflict memory on discursive use of the metaphor. The results show how metaphor entailments may vary according to the kinds of war made salient in discourse. Several forms of discursive use grounded in linking metaphorical and literal senses of war are identified, as creating specific local meanings, which in the case area observed worked to relate representations of threat to dominant instrumentalizations of historical memory and ongoing nationalist discourses. Beyond the local context, the findings are used to discuss some aspects of pandemic-time WAR metaphor use important both for the theorizing of adversarial metaphors in public discourse, and for more nuanced analyses of the discourses of crisis.

Keywords: WAR metaphor, COVID-19, crisis discourse, nationalism, memory

1. Introduction

If one thing has been evident from the proliferating language and communication research on the discourses of the COVID-19 crisis, it is that the understanding of the pandemic is “a metaphorical one from the beginning” (Olza et al., 2021). Communicating a new and unpredictable emergency has largely rested on figurative language, especially in the first months. In particular, the metaphorical

representations that very soon came to stand out included varied forms of military metaphors, seen in announcements of *war* with the *invisible enemy*, *battles* and *frontlines* – a pattern not too surprising given the known productivity of the WAR domain for conceptualizing both illness and important sociopolitical matters (Flusberg et al., 2017; Jaspal & Nerlich, 2020).

Indeed, in many parts of the world, the WAR metaphors soon became an important tool for making sense of the new situation, as well as an important element of crisis communication and political discourse used to frame new crisis responses. In many contexts, it has been argued to introduce new forms of authoritarian, polarizing and ‘coronationalist’ (Bouckaert et al., 2020) discourses, which pave the way to new forms of oppositional thought in times of ongoing political crises and growing inequality. This in part explains the unprecedented and persisting attention to the ‘old’ topic of WAR metaphors that we are witnessing in both scholarship and public commentary. A vast amount of criticism from diverse social agents, including linguists, historians, politicians, healthcare workers, and citizens, has been directed at this public conceptual frame, to the point that the WAR metaphor observed by linguists, and the militarization of public discourse observed in the humanities more broadly (cf. Erll, 2020) in itself seem to be turning into a sub-area of inquiry. Moreover, analyses of the discourses of the pandemic beyond the as yet dominant core of metaphor research in western/anglophone contexts are beginning to highlight some often ignored aspects of the WAR metaphor, especially the fact that it is in no way an established, globally parallel, or statically functioning framing device.

On the one hand, WAR is a major conceptual anchor in structuring various aspects of human experience (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980), and is itself an important human experience globally: whether through direct experience of participating in real wars, or through indirect experience via interpersonal and mediated communication (cf. Ritchie, 2003). This pervasiveness at the same time makes WAR a good case in point to consider global conceptual meanings and local realizations, as well as the macro-level social contexts and micro-level realizations on the level of texts. For one thing, the entailments of this pervasive metaphor can vary significantly depending on specific discursive realizations, such as the different forms of metaphor extension, or analogies with literal senses of concrete earlier wars. Indeed, the use of extended WAR metaphors that conceptually bring together the present and the past, as observed in some analyses from areas with relatively recent conflict experience – from morale-boosting comparisons to collectively survived hardship (Banjeglav & Moll, 2021) to polarizing discourses of heroic nationhood (Salamurović, 2020) – reflect patterns in discourse whose more detailed understanding could complement existing accounts of this metaphor in linguistic scholarship.

The present paper aims to contribute to the growing body of work on the pandemic-time use of the WAR metaphor in public discourse, by focusing specifically on the post-Yugoslav, post-conflict states of Serbia and Croatia. Rather than seeing the metaphor use as essentially different in such settings, or focusing on conceptual effects, the analysis looks at the discursive realizations of WAR metaphors, their extensions in text, and the entailments created by references to real war. Beyond the local context, the findings on metaphor entailments and relations of literal and metaphorical meaning will be highlighted as relevant both for the theorizing of adversarial metaphors in public discourse, and for more nuanced analyses of the discourses of crisis.

2. Background

The WAR metaphor is used in the understanding of various human difficulties and challenges, as one of the primary conceptual tools in the western world (Lakoff, 1992). It is frequently used to talk about diseases (Demjén & Semino, 2016), but far beyond, it has long been described as important for conceptualizing varied forms of individual and collective difficulties, from cancer to climate change (Atanasova & Koteyko, 2017; Semino et al., 2018). In cognitive terms, the productivity of the WAR metaphor has been further explained by its grounding in the primary metaphor DIFFICULTIES ARE OPPONENTS, with the salience and cognitive accessibility of this metaphor further enforced by frequent usage in contemporary discourse (Grady, 1997). In critical discourse studies, the use of war rhetoric in public arenas has been a recurrent topic. Issues addressed in this body of work range from the ‘wars’ on specific social threats such as drug-trafficking or crime, to the legitimization of political action by pinpointing ‘an enemy’ (see Flusberg et al., 2017). These discourse-oriented discussions have often drawn on psycholinguistic research, which has repeatedly shown potentially problematic framing effects of WAR metaphors when reasoning about solutions to social issues (e.g. Thibodeau & Boroditsky, 2011). In health crisis communication, conceptualizing illness as war has been amply discussed ever since Susan Sontag’s seminal *Illness as Metaphor* (1978), while the general productivity of the WAR domain for conceptualizing illness is long described (e.g. Flusberg et al. 2017). In the case of diseases, perhaps more prominently of all, linguists and metaphor researchers have for many years pointed to the potential negative effects of framing diseases as battles (e.g. Demjén & Semino, 2016; Hauser & Schwarz, 2015), though it has also been emphasized that these metaphors could be empowering depending on the context (Semino et al., 2018).

After the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, the prominence of WAR metaphors in crisis communication was soon taken up by discourse analysts and cognitive linguists, tapping into all this previous work, while bringing forth both new insights and new public criticism. As some analysts observe, the proliferation of research and commentary has also brought “a ‘love-hate’ relationship with the WAR metaphor, to a point that we can observe a ‘war’ on war metaphors” (Despot & Ostroški Anić, 2021, p.7). Overall, for better or worse, research certainly confirms the dominance of the WAR metaphor in pandemic discourse throughout the world. The metaphor appears to be cross-cultural (e.g. Atuhura, 2022; Charteris-Black, 2021; Olza et al., 2021; Rajandran, 2020) and similarly used in media, political and health discourses (e.g. Dada et al., 2021; Marey-Sarwan et al., 2022). Corpus-based studies (e.g. Chatti, 2021) show notable co-occurrence of military terms and the ‘coronavirus’ and the ‘COVID-19’ lemmas, while analyses of political speeches from various parts of the world show similarly predominant use of military metaphors (Castro Seixas, 2021). In the discourse of social media, for instance, Wicke and Bolognesi (2020) analyzed the discussions on COVID-19 on Twitter and showed that among the most common figurative frames detected, namely WAR, MONSTER, STORM and TSUNAMI, WAR is used the most frequently. In response to these observed patterns, the #ReframeCovid initiative (Olza et al., 2021) set out to critically reflect on the use of WAR metaphors for COVID-19, as well as to collect alternatives, and has by now resulted in a valuable cross-linguistic repository. Moreover, subversive, ironic and satirical uses of the WAR metaphor have also been noted (Musolff, 2022), pointing to notable meta-linguistic awareness when it comes to the new crisis vocabularies. More generally, most existing discourse-oriented studies emphasize framing effects, as relevant to thinking about the implications of pandemic-time WAR metaphor use. From this angle, researchers have voiced concerns that WAR metaphors may legitimize authoritarian measures that could in fact be disproportionate (Chapman et al., 2020), and go beyond the specific response to the pandemic, especially when drawing on a “potentially fuzzy boundary between the literal and metaphorical status of military references during the pandemic” (Semino, 2021, p.52).

Recent analyses also suggest that the WAR metaphor is a good case in point for considering local realizations of global discourses, as well as the relations of ‘macro-level’ social contexts and ‘micro-level’ patterns (Fairclough, 2010) in text (Berrocal et al., 2021). Discursive metaphor studies suggest the important role of metaphor extension (Semino, 2008) in shaping the micro-level meanings of well-established metaphors, often in entire narratives that give a specific ‘colour’ to the war being described (Bogetić, 2022). Metaphor extensions and realizations in text also affect the entailments of war created in that way: What kind of war is it? Who is fighting on the opposing sides? What are the in-groups, out-groups, affiliated

groups (cf. social categorization, Koller, 2012)? Discursively referring to specific kinds of war, or specific kinds of enemies – or even, relating the metaphorical descriptions to specific past, literal wars – will affect the key entailments of the metaphor. This requires careful attention to metaphor context, extension across text, micro-level textual forms and macro-level social contexts.

This also brings us to one aspect of the WAR metaphor that has not received much empirical attention in linguistics: its potential to connect the senses of wars real and figurative, past and present. The tendency for crisis discourses to resort to comparisons with the past are well attested in the pandemic references to *war*: Queen Elizabeth II compared this situation to that of World War One, while the German Prime Minister said the challenge was the greatest since after 1945, to use but a couple of examples. In pandemic-time humanities research, especially political science and memory studies, attention to the WAR metaphor in times of COVID-19 has come precisely from this pattern, with scholars stressing that in times of crises, memory of the (conflict) past becomes the main staple of political discourse (Erll, 2020), which carries strong implications for (re)constructions of group belonging, collective responses and collective pasts and futures.

While (post-)conflict areas may offer a productive space to examine such representations, the common reference to past wars observed in pandemic communication globally highlights the potential relevance of historical analogies for figurative representation much more broadly. The shape of such figurative language will nevertheless differ in different textual and social contexts. In one study of early pandemic public discourse in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia, for instance, Banjeglav and Moll (2021) highlight the prominence of extended metaphors and historical analogies, suggesting that memory of the conflict which had accompanied the collapse of the socialist state has affected the pandemic-time metaphorical crisis communication. Other analyses of pandemic discourse in the area and beyond highlight conflicting social conceptualizations (Bogetić 2022, Berrocal et al. 2021) that point to the need to better understand the interactions among the global crisis, military metaphor, and local discourses of collectivity and solidarity that in this crisis appear to intersect along not always predictable lines. In this paper, the locale of former Yugoslavia is taken as a rich context in which to investigate the discursive realizations of the WAR metaphor, and to examine the micro-level realizations and different possible metaphor entailments in different textual and sociopolitical contexts.

3. Data and methods

The specialized corpus used for the study comprises news articles from Serbia and Croatia relating to the pandemic, published in early-pandemic time (March 2020-May 2020) in the major online news outlets (*Politika*, *Večernje novosti*, *Blic* and *B92* in Serbia; *Jutarnji list*, *Večernji list*, *24sata*, index.hr in Croatia). The corpus collection procedure involved manual topic-driven collection of the texts from the newspaper online archives, based on a set of key lemmas with 5+ hits (*koronavirus*, *korona*, *kovid*, *pandemija*). This included a total of 55 texts, 39,162 words in the Serbian and 76 texts, 34,551 words in the Croatian sub-corpus; the texts span different forms of articles, from reports of politicians' statements, through reports on pandemic progression, to other accounts and opinions by public figures or journalists themselves. While the comparatively small corpus size is a potential limitation of the study, especially in quantitative terms, it allows a coherent look at the mainstream media discourse on the pandemic in the two states, and was found advantageous for our purposes of mainly qualitative discursive analysis of metaphor use.

The focus on the two post-socialist, post-conflict states once part of Yugoslavia entails shared elements of context in many ways, but must be understood as drawing on distinct political discourses and distinct political paths since the violent breakup of the country in the early 1990s. The choice of the two states as the most studied in this region has downsides, but is found productive to narrow down the scope, and is grounded in the author's familiarity with the context. The analysis does not aim at a comparative focus, but certain similarities and differences are observed as relevant to the discursive context. The very notion of 'post-conflict' is always problematic, and is here understood in the loose sense of relatively recent conflict events with continuing political legacy of past violence (cf. Brown et al. 2008). War discourses are approached via attested realizations in discourse, rather than a priori elements of metaphor use, or a distinguishing factor in metaphor effects. The macro level context is nevertheless important for the analysis, acknowledging the notable role played by the memory of the 1990s wars in both contemporary political discourses and the lived realities of the citizens.

The method of (WAR) metaphor identification followed the MIPVU procedure (Steen et al., 2010), and its version modified for Serbian/Serbo-Croatian (Bogetić et al., 2019). MIPVU identifies metaphors based on the contrast between contextual meanings and more basic contemporary meanings. If the contextual meaning of a word could be explained in relation to the basic meaning, the lexical unit was marked as metaphoric; only the WAR domain lexical units related to topically key lemmas (*koronavirus*, *virus*, *COVID*, *kovid*, *pandemija*) were retained in the final analysis file. In identifying the metaphorical expressions that belong

to the WAR domain, it was important to avoid lumping together other potential vocabulary of, for instance, competition and violence under WAR (e.g. *winning, beating*).¹ Thus, all expressions identified which had clear military reference were included (*war*, as well as, specifically: *battle* ('bitka' Ser-Cro / 'boj' Slo); *invasion* ('invazija' Ser-Cro, Slo); *siege* ('opsada' Ser-Cro); *mobilisation* ('mobilizacija' Ser-Cro, Slo); *soldier* (vojnik Ser-Cro);² also, the more ambiguous ones were included when used within metaphor extension alongside *war*³ (e.g. *winning this war despite human victims*), where classification within the domain of WAR is textually justified; finally the more ambiguous ones were included when association with literal meanings justified it (*fight like we fought back in the war*).

The ensuing analysis largely followed the principles of Critical Metaphor Analysis (Charteris-Black, 2004), combining an interest in the conceptual elements of metaphor use and the social and political meanings realized in discourse. In this regard, particular attention was paid to metaphor extension, with its potential to create metaphorical frames and narratives, as well as to metaphor entailments observed in discourse. While the focus remains on the micro level of the texts and discourse (Fairclough, 2010), the analysis pays attention to the macro level of social context contributing to the meanings of WAR metaphors.

4. Analysis

4.1 Non-extended and extended realizations of the WAR metaphor

The first step in the analysis was to quantify all the WAR domain metaphorical expressions identified, and to classify them in terms of realization (non-extended use or part of metaphor extension). While different definitions of metaphor extension are available, it is here understood in the most basic sense of belonging to the same source domain, i.e. "when at least two metaphorically used words belonging to different phrases describe the same target domain/scenario in terms of the same source domain/scenario" (Semino, 2008, p.25). All quantification was

1. Arguably, *winning, losing* and *beating* may just as well belong to a sports or game domain, while even *fight* may refer to sports or other fights (and their relations can be blurred, cf. Ritchie, 2003).

2. Of course, many others are possible, but only these were attested in the corpus.

3. Other military terms besides *war* could have been used, but were not attested in extensions of the kind.

done on the lexical level of metaphorical expressions, with each instance counted, including repetition.⁴

Table 1. Metaphorical expressions from the WAR domain

	Non-extended use	Extended use	Metaphorical expressions (Total)
Croatia	14	81	95
Serbia	11	62	73

The analysis confirms that WAR metaphors feature prominently in both the Croatian and Serbian datasets, with approximately one occurrence per one text. Further, the results reveal a prominence of metaphor extension: the vast majority of the WAR metaphor realizations are part of extension via related expressions, accounting for 62 expressions (86.1%) in the Serbian and 81 (85.9%) in the Croatian data respectively.

Non-extended metaphor use is limited to several instances in each dataset. It seems particularly fit for news titles, with the majority ((9) out of (14) in Croatian, (7) out of (11) in Serbian) indeed found in similarly sounding article titles:

- (1) *Srpski rat s koronom*
‘The Serbian war with corona’⁵ [SrCorp]
- (2) *Hrvataska u ratu sa koronavirusom*
‘Croatia at war with the coronavirus’ [CroCorp]

A large proportion of the metaphorical expressions occur in extended use, i.e. as part of metaphor extension. Some of these involve two related expressions, such as references to *winning* or *losing* the *war*. On the other hand, we can generally observe a number of more elaborate metaphorical descriptions that draw on a range of metaphorical lexis from the WAR domain. The expressions in metaphor extension often cluster in particular segments of text (cf. Semino, 2008), while also spanning across titles, introductions, and concluding statements.

While a lot of similar, almost formulaic metaphor use can be observed across the texts, the metaphorical expressions are used to discuss varied aspects of the situation. In the media discourses, they naturally come from varied social actors’ voices, such as those of political theorists assessing the situation (3), or journalists themselves bringing interviews with healthcare workers at their workplace (4):

4. E.g. in a text commenting on *the war against COVID and our future in this war*, with no other metaphorical realizations, *war* will be counted as two instances, non-extended (since the expressions do not belong to different phrases).

5. All translations are the author’s.

- (3) *U situaciji kada se država bori da sačuva što je više moguće ljudskih života izloženih pandemiji, hrvatski premijer proglasio je rat virusu... Plenković u taj rat ne može krenuti sam, i ne treba. Taj rat tiče se svih nas. Drugo je pitanje sada kako "naoružani" ulazimo u taj rat protiv virusa. "Vojnike", zdravstvene radnike i javne službe imamo, no u svemu ostalome, [...] ovisimo o drugima. Neka postave, ako treba, i "vojnu" upravu koja će blokirati sabotere*
 'In a situation where the country is fighting to save as many people's lives as possible in the face of the pandemic, the Croatian Prime Minister has declared war on the virus. Plenković cannot start this war alone, nor should he. This war concerns us all. The second question is how well "armed" we are going into this war against the virus. We have "soldiers", health workers and public services, but for everything else, [...] we depend on others. Let them set up, if necessary, a "war" administration that will block the saboteurs.' [CroCorp]
- (4) *U prostoru za uzorkovanje tri profesionalke, u punoj "bojnoj" opremi. Rat protiv virusa traži da se ratnici na prvoj liniji dobro zaštite od neprijatelja. Na licima maske, preko kose kape, nad odijelom skafander i još vizir preko očiju. Prva bojna "Higijenski". [...] Razgovaramo o virusu koji je u samo pola godine izmijenio svijet, nije njemu stalo da nas pobijedi, on "samo" teži suživotu.*
 'In the sampling room, three professional women, in full "combat" gear. The war against the virus requires that the warriors on the frontline protect themselves well from the enemy. On the face, a mask, a cap over the hair, a visor over the eyes. The first battle line of "the Hygiene Section". We are talking about the virus that has changed the world, it doesn't care about defeating us, it "only" strives for coexistence.' [CroCorp]

Similar metaphoricity is observed in the reports of the more official announcements of national leaders, referring to the new hardship and the best ways to react. The first announcement of the pandemic in Serbia by its president A. Vučić on March 2020 is a good illustration:

- (5) *Poštovani građani, Srbija je od danas u ratu protiv nevidljivog i opasnog protivnika, koju naša zemlja mora da pobedi. Ovo će za nas biti najteža bitka za naš narod, bitka za naše stare i bolesne, oni su meta ovog žestokog napada. Moramo da čuvamo sve ali su oni pre svega meta ovog žestokog napada.*
 'Dear citizens, as of today Serbia is at war with an invisible and dangerous enemy, at which our country has to win. This will be the hardest battle for our nation, a battle for our elderly and ill, they are the target of this fierce attack. We must take care of everyone but they are above all the target of this fierce attack.' [SrCorp]

The elaborate metaphorical account of the situation gains meaning precisely via the varied expressions from the WAR domain, including the idea of a *battle* as a

stage in a war, and the mandatoriness of *winning*. It is also important to observe the extended metaphors that resurface later in Vučić's speech and the report:

- (6) *Vučić je rekao da se sve mere preduzimaju kako bi se sačuvala zemlja, jer predaja nije opcija, nikada nije bila opcija za Srbiju. Vučić je istakao da smo od 1804. godine i od uspostavljanja moderne srpske države, "ginuli, ginuli, ginuli", te da je dobro da poštujemo istoriju, tradiciju i pokazujemo koliko volimo zemlju. 'Vučić has said that all measures are being taken to save the country, because surrender is not an option, it has never been an option for Serbia. Vučić emphasized that since 1804 we have been "getting killed, killed and killed", so it is good to respect history, tradition and show how much we love our country.* [SrCorp]

In this segment the explicit, literal reference to past wars further shapes the frame for understanding the situation: the *hardest battle* yet for our people gains meaning and emotional strength via shared knowledge of the other historical battles known to Serbia.

Very similar WAR domain metaphorical expressions in extension can be observed in the national announcement of Croatia's national secretary:

- (7) *U ovim zahtjevnim vremenima kada smo pogođeni Korona krizom, upravo ovaj obiteljski stupanj zajedništva podsjeća na '91. kada smo svi disali kao jedan. [...] U ovom ratu protiv virusa, ostajemo ujedinjeni u vrijednostima zbog kojih smo 90-ih bili hrabri i odgovorni jedni za druge. Tada je bilo taka, tako je i danas. [...] Zato pozivam sve da budemo vojnički disciplinirani, hrabri, nesebični, da cijenimo naše medicinare. Oni su naši vojnici današnjice. 'In these demanding times when we are hit by the corona crisis, this family togetherness reminds us of '91 when we all breathed like one. [...] During this war with the virus, we stay united in the values for which we were brave and responsible for each other in the 1990s. It was like that then, and it will be like that now. [...] That is why I invite everyone to have soldier discipline, bravery, selflessness, to value our medical workers. They are our soldiers of today.'* [CroCorp]

Like in the Serbian example, there are several extended metaphors from the WAR domain, accompanied by reference to earlier war, creating combined senses of national victimisation, patriotism and heroicism throughout history. Here the reference draws explicitly on what is locally known as the 'Homeland War', or the 'War of Independence', which has an important place in Croatia's memory politics.

Overall, looking at metaphor extensions in the different examples, it is possible to get a glimpse of the wider discourses of collectivity, solidarity and difference in pandemic times. Extended metaphors and their discursive/textual context –

including the accompanying literal comparisons – may be particularly useful for understanding metaphor entailments and micro-level realizations. In this case, entailments provide further insights into questions such as: What kind of war is this? Who is the in-group, or the out-group? Is the ‘new war’ about global or national solidarity, or about other kinds of collectivity? Even the several examples above are illustrative in this regard, most notably reflecting the framing of the in-group in national terms (*the Serbian war; Croatia losing the war*), with the virus as the *enemy*.

There seems to be another form of use to observe in this respect, pertaining to metaphorical and literal uses of war, as illustrated in the two national addresses. The ‘kind of war’ going on, when represented as being ‘like our earlier wars’, carries further layers of meaning, effected specifically in textual juxtapositions of literal and figurative war reference. Below we thus turn such forms of extended metaphors use in more more detail.

4.2 Extended metaphor realizations: Interaction with literal uses of *war*

While it is in theory possible to encounter non-extended metaphors with literal counterparts,⁶ such instances are not attested in the data, and references to literal war appear more suitable for accompanying and complementing extended metaphorical descriptions. Conversely, while we do of course find many examples of metaphor extension with no literal reference at all (like 1–4 above, and the many accounts of e.g. *winning the war against COVID*), extensions with parallel literal references merit attention as having distinct form and entailment meanings.

The discursive realizations of this kind of metaphor use can differ, and be more or less direct, as seen in descriptions such as *the war like our earlier wars* or *being the hardest war yet*. An attempt to quantify these occurrences and classify them according to discursive forms is summarized in Table 2, while the forms are further explained below.

The findings show that extended metaphorical realizations are often accompanied by some form of literal war reference: in both contexts, more than a third of the instances respectively are found to involve some discursive relation or comparison to real wars. Relation to literal senses was determined in textual context, including both the direct syntactic relations and relations to war references in text (more on this is below). Some instances are nevertheless best grouped as ‘Unclear’, such as references to a *new war* (as opposed to the past ones?) without enough context, instances that seem to repeat other wordings (*surrender has never been an option*, possibly reflecting the Serbian president’s words from his earlier

6. E.g. any single occurrence of *war against COVID and our nation’s past wars*.

Table 2. Expressions occurring as part of extended metaphors and relations to literal use*

	Relation to literal use						No relation to literal use	Unclear	Total			
	Direct relation		Indirect relation		Metaphor blurring							
	Example	No.	Example	No.	Example	No.						
Croatia	<i>We won that war, we'll win this one as well.</i>	9	<i>Croatia is at war again. [Like in 1991, ...]</i>	22	<i>In every war there is a traitors' column.</i>	3	34	<i>We are losing the war against covid</i>	43	<i>We are fighting a new war.</i>	4	81
Serbia	<i>Serbia has survived many wars, it will survive this war as well.</i>	3	<i>This will be the hardest battle for our people. [We have been getting killed since ...]</i>	15	<i>Since 1805, we have been getting killed.</i>	6	24	<i>The war against the virus needs warriors</i>	30	<i>Surrender has never been an option.</i>	8	62

* The table presents example extracts of each category for illustration; note that these are realizations of individual expressions, not showing the full extension. The coding necessarily rested on careful consideration of the full textual context.

address?), and all occurrences where connection to wars mentioned in a text are not fully clear in context (full data coding can be found at <https://osf.io/q9a7b/>).

Overall, while coding of discursive relations of this kind can never be a fully clear-cut process, beyond quantification as a goal in itself (especially given the corpus size), the findings clearly suggest that associations with literal reference uses are relevant to the discourse. The results will be more important here for illustrating this specific discursive use and its potential social meanings.⁷

In terms of form, then, three types of usage are identified in the datasets. The comparison of the current situation to real past wars often takes the form of a direct juxtaposition of figurative and literal wars, as *that war and this one*. Specif-

7. In terms of frequency, we should also bear in mind the potential impact of particular social actors and their repeated framings. While the discourse analyzed contains voices of diverse social actors, it is possible, for instance, that the Serbian findings are affected by the president's early statement of the *hardest national battle* and *surrender not being an option*, which gets taken up by journalists and others; the Croatian literal associations, on the other hand, appear more diverse, so this does not seem to be of note.

ically, the discursive form can be described as juxtaposition with direct reference, where the metaphorical and literal uses of *war* co-appear explicitly in the text, often with a direct sentential link. The following examples reporting the words of citizen interviewees are an illustration:

- (8) *Dobili smo taj rat, dobićemo i ovaj*
 ‘We won that war, we will win this one as well.’ [CroCorp]
- (9) *Srbija je kroz istorije preživela mnoge ratove, preživeće i rat protiv virusa.*
 ‘Serbia has survived many wars in history, it’ll survive the war against the virus.’ [SrCorp]

The sentential link is often realized via metaphor marking, mainly via demonstratives (*that one*_{Lit.} and *this one*_{Met.}). The time reference of ‘then and now’, of old and new generations, also plays a role, realized in references such as *that war*_{Lit.} and *our new one*_{Met.}, or in other explicit juxtapositions of the real past war and the new generation’s *war*:

- (10) *Generacija premlada za Domovinski rat dobila je priliku da se drži svoga, koronskoga rata.*
 ‘The generation too young for the Homeland War got a chance to stick to its own, corona war.’ [CroCorp]

Above all, this kind of use allows making sense of the current *fight*s through comparisons with an earlier war situation, as in the following response of a Croatian psychologist:

- (11) *Brojna su upozorenja o očuvanju psihe nacije u izazovnim vremenima poput situacije u kojoj se borimo s korona virusom. Prije 25 godina imali smo Domovinski rat u kojemu su svakodnevno ginuli borci i civili. Situacija je bila teža nego danas. Kao što smo preživjeli tu situaciju, preživjet ćemo i ovu.*
 ‘There are many warnings about saving the nation’s mental health in challenging times like the situation where we are fighting the corona virus. 25 years ago we had the Homeland War where fighters and civilians died daily. The situation was harder than today. Like we survived that situation, we will survive this one.’ [CroCorp]

Connections of this kind again involve some level of extension across the texts,⁸ which acts to further explain the metaphorical representation or make it more evocative. When a specific war is referenced (e.g. the *Homeland War* and 1991), this has the potential to create specific entailments, such as reinforcing the framing of

8. The examples are kept shorter in order to focus on discursive forms, though many of the realizations are part of longer and multiple metaphor extensions across text.

the in-group in national terms. In such pandemic discourses, the solidarity evoked is largely constructed in terms of an essentially Croatian or Serbian unity and freedom *once fought for* which is at the test again.

A second form of metaphor use with similar rhetorical effects involves juxtaposition through indirect comparison, without explicit linking to a literal war (i.e. without direct sentential connection of 'this war' and 'a real one'), but with clear reference to other wars, usually mentioned elsewhere in the text. The titles and openings of articles in March 2020, often citing leading politicians (as in (12) and (13) below), would repeatedly draw on metaphorical references to a new *war*, evoking less or more specified (*again*, or *after 30 years*) war situations, albeit without direct sentential connection:

(12) *Srbija je ponovo u ratu.*
'Serbia is at war again.' [SrCorp]

(13) *Posle 30 godina, ponovo smo u ratu.*
'After 30 years, we are once again at war.' [CroCorp]

Again, even when the real war reference is not immediately clear, discursive marking plays a role in evoking the literal, largely historical sense, in this case most notably involving markers of temporal reference (a war *again*, *once again*, *today*, a *modern* war). This adds a new nuance of meaning to the metaphorical war, in that it is similar to some other previous war.

In reference to the 'war happening again' metaphorical extension often also serves the purposes of explaining this war's nature and specificity, often resorted to by leading politicians in interviews:

(14) *Opet smo u ratu, samo što je neprijatelj sada nevidljiv. Ovaj rat sigurno će biti dobiven, ali uz velike ljudske i materijalne žrtve.*
'We are at war again, only the enemy is invisible this time. This war will surely be won, but with great human and material victims.' [CroCorp]

The notion of 'a war happening again' provides a frame to interpret the situation, constructing a combined sense of a need for discipline which may justify measures of the national leadership. Aside from the comparison to real war, however, this type of metaphor use also gains meaning through the temporal sense of contemporaneity, and especially repetition, in the notion of wars happening *anew*, *again and again*, and striking an in-group collective body typically imagined in rather specific, Serbian and Croatian terms respectively.

The idea of 'being at war again' points to another complex element of the discourse. The relation of *war* metaphorical representations to *war* literal senses can be more or less specified, as a concrete historical war (e.g. the specific, *Homeland war*, as in most of the above examples in Croatia) or a less specified, but clearly

'real', non-metaphorical past war (e.g. in many examples of Serbia⁹ being *at war again*). The level of specificity is not always possible to ascertain or code. Still, this is a factor that may further influence the entailments of established metaphors: specific references to concrete wars, as with the *1990s war* or *the Homeland war* common in my corpus will carry distinct sociopolitical implications for local discourse, as compared to non-specific reference to some of *our past wars*, or comparisons with *every war* in general. I thus focus on literal uses overall, observing the historical references where appropriate, but this distinction may merit attention in future studies using bigger datasets.

The levels of specification can vary in the form of the literal or metaphorical meaning itself. Thus, finally, a third discursive metaphor form observed involves what can be described as a blurred comparison: a use of WAR lexis which involves a fuzzy boundary between the literal and metaphorical sense, so that the meaning of the utterance involves both of these senses together. This form of use is comparatively far less frequent in the datasets than the other two (6 instances in Serbian, 2 in Croatian). Beyond frequency, however, it reflects a specific discursive metaphor use, with specific discursive effects, which merits attention in its own right; here we will try to examine the mechanism itself.

Like the above example of the Serbian president's observation that *we've been getting killed, killed and killed* for centuries, the pandemic being only a continuation – is one illustration of this type of use. Conceptually, this statement brings together the war killing over time and the current *killing* by COVID-19, where the metaphorical killing in pandemic times gains a specific additional sense of historically unceasing suffering.

The concluding sentence in that same address to the nation enforces this representation further, via repetition, via references to *war* throughout the speech, and via more use of blurred comparison to round-off the whole representation of the *fight* ahead in positive terms:

- (15) *Nećemo da pokazujemo evropsku, već srpsku solidarnost. [...] Predaja nikada nije bila opcija, i nikada neće biti opcija za Srbiju. Borićemo se i pobedićemo – zaključio je predsednik Srbije.*⁶

We will not show European, but Serbian solidarity. [...] Surrender has never been an option, and will not be an option for Serbia. We shall fight and we shall win – concluded the president of Serbia. [SrCorp]

While *fighting* and *winning* clearly metaphorically refer to the new situation, the *surrender* that has *never* been an option refers to both the historical heroicism

9. Where the more general reference appears somewhat more common than in the Croatian dataset.

of Serbia's true past wars, as well as to the upcoming resistance in the current situation; the blending of real and figurative, past, present (or future) reference enforces the heroic national representation and adds a historical dimension to obviously present-day and future references of fighting the COVID-19 pandemic, also justifying the direct political framing of Serbian, rather than pan-European solidarity.

Again, while this metaphorical process is comparatively less common in the data, it exhibits specific implications for discursive meaning. Statements of this kind create blurred images of metaphorical and real war, constructing the crisis as an extension of known troubles. The fuzzy metaphoricity (cf. Semino, 2021) may also be seen to subtly justify extreme measures, by blurring the lines between health crisis and real military situations, in the period when first legal measures started to be introduced. In the case of small states divided by an EU border, while both characterized by immigration, work abroad and massive border crowds of those refused entry into their respective countries, the fuzzy framings of wartime produced grounds for imagining the kind of solidarity to (not) be held on to in times of crisis, with tangible effects in the lived realities of thousands. Arguably, the process of war blurring has important potential to enforce conceptualisations of threat, and normalize divisions into 'victims' and 'enemies', 'us' and 'others', reinforcing what clearly emerges as "narrow emergency frames of collective (usually national) identity" (Erl, 2020) which conceptually leave many (e.g. other nations and ethnicities, migrant workers, foreign refugees, slum inhabitants) outside of pandemic public discourses.

5. Discussion and conclusions

Similar to what is noted in related research from other parts of the world (e.g. Atuhura, 2022; Charteris-Black, 2021), the WAR metaphor was found to be an important tool of representation in the Croatian and Serbian public discourses of the early COVID-19 period. The representation of a country at war is mobilized for varied communicative purposes, in order to make sense of the current situation, justify official measures, or allow specific sociopolitical positioning. The findings lend further support to existing findings on the ubiquity of WAR metaphors in health discourse, as well as in crisis communication.

In the analysis, expressions from the WAR domain were found to largely occur as part of metaphor extensions, often in elaborate metaphorical narratives spanning across the text. In the early months of the pandemic, these extended metaphors were found useful by different social actors for explaining the collective (usually nationally-framed) situation and emphasizing the need for discipline

and likelihood of victory. It is also of note that a large proportion of such expressions occurring as part of metaphor extension were found to involve some form of discursive relation to literal meanings of *war*, in specific references to past conflict in the Yugoslav area. Such discursive patterns overall draw attention to the entailments of this pervasive metaphor, which can significantly vary depending on the kind of war made salient in the text. The present paper identified three forms of representations in metaphor extension that combine literal and figurative senses of *war*, but the discursive and conceptual effects of such combined use will merit attention from larger corpus-based analysis in the future.

For one thing, beyond this single metaphor, the described relations of metaphorical and literal senses in discourse may play a specific role in varied forms of conceptual representations. We have seen that constructions such as *our eternal wars* collapse both a metaphorical and literal sense within a single lexical unit, where the meaning of the metaphor draws from the literal meaning of the word, while the effect of the resulting meaning is more than the sum of its parts. Examples of this kind are also relevant for metaphor identification, as we find a single lexical unit that at the same time contains a metaphorical and literal meaning.¹⁰ In the case of *war*, we have seen the historical sense to be crucial in the process, but other forms of literal meaning can just as well interact with figurative meanings, in ways that go far beyond this single metaphor or this single discursive context.

From a broader angle, the findings tap into some observations on crisis discourse from other areas of the humanities, which nevertheless rarely come in touch with linguistic metaphor scholarship. Most notably, this pertains to the conceptual relevance of 'mnemonic imagination' (Keightley & Pickering, 2012) in discourses of social change: the repeated finding that in times of crises, memory of the past becomes a staple of public discourse (Erll, 2020) which influences how socio-political phenomena are conceptualized. In a way, the collective pasts and struggles that are, but also those that are *not* referred to – consider the total absence of any direct reference to e.g. World War II, the Yugoslav anti-fascist struggle, etc. – create specific metaphor entailments, with implications for imagining the present moment, as well as the collective pasts, and possible or desired futures. In this process, the WAR metaphor is an important tool, bringing together the conceptual, rhetorical and political senses of the situation into a strong collective emergency frame.

10. MIPVU would here employ the WIDLII ('when-in-doubt-leave-it-in') category; still, the uses that are undoubtedly both literal and metaphorical may be relevant depending on the type of study.

On the whole, the analysis confirms the productiveness of WAR metaphors for framing crisis situations and collective responses, given its entailments and possible social meanings. Above all, WAR metaphors have specific potential to determine who is at war, who the ‘we’ refers to, and what needs to be done; the discursive shapes of extended metaphors, and the possibility to link metaphors to literal meanings of conflict, all carry further potential for creating metaphor entailments, as well as for steering social meanings in public and political discourse. At the same time, historically, the resonances of war are never a staple of the past only. As seen in the post-Yugoslav area, the notion of war simultaneously representing traumatic collective experience and a subject of ever-growing revisionist memory politics, is an important conceptual tool that shapes understandings of social life spanning politics, crises, solidarity and citizen rights across time. In this sense, the use of WAR metaphors in discourses of the pandemic is a prime reminder of the multifacetedness of metaphorical representation, and the various discursive, affective and cognitive nuances that merit attention as interacting in the creation of social meaning. Evidently, given the great lay meta-linguistic interest in metaphors in public communication – exemplified well in the current “wars of the war metaphor” (Despot & Ostroški Anić, 2021) – adversarial metaphors are an important tool for adopting, resisting, subverting and rethinking the existing framings of the near future society, especially in times of newly competing visions of the future that accompany the growing social inequalities and political crises of our day.

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